

BGE Myxohares DMP

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes how data generated within the MyxoHares case study will be handled throughout its lifecycle, from collection and processing to long-term preservation and reuse. The project integrates whole-genome sequencing data from Iberian hares with pathogen detection to investigate host-pathogen interactions underlying differential susceptibility to myxomatosis.

The purpose of this DMP is to ensure that all data are managed in accordance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), comply with legal and ethical requirements (including Nagoya Protocol considerations), and are made available to the scientific community and relevant stakeholders where appropriate. The DMP also defines procedures for data storage, backup, metadata standards, controlled access to sensitive information, and long-term archiving in trusted repositories.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Biodiversity Genomics Europe
(corda____he::101059492)

Researchers

João Pedro Marques (0000-0001-9834-1361)

Organizations

Associação BIOPOLIS - Rede de Investigação em Biodiversidade e
Biologia Evolutiva

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [BGE Myxohares DMP](#)

Description:

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes how data generated within the MyxoHares case study will be handled throughout its lifecycle, from collection and processing to long-term preservation and reuse. The project integrates whole-genome sequencing data from Iberian hares with pathogen detection to investigate host-pathogen interactions underlying differential susceptibility to myxomatosis.

The purpose of this DMP is to ensure that all data are managed in accordance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), comply with legal and ethical requirements (including Nagoya Protocol considerations), and are made available to the scientific community and relevant stakeholders where appropriate. The DMP also defines procedures for data storage, backup, metadata standards, controlled access to sensitive information, and long-term archiving in trusted repositories.

Researchers:

[João Pedro Marques \(0000-0001-9834-1361\)](#)

Organizations:

[Associação BIOPOLIS - Rede de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Biologia Evolutiva](#)

Contact: [Marques João Pedro \(joao.marques@cibio.up.pt\)](mailto:joao.marques@cibio.up.pt)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Biodiversity Genomics Europe \(corda_____he::101059492\)](#)

Project: [Cite Project](#)

3. License

License: [AFL-3.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

BGE Myxohares DMP

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes how data generated within the MyxoHares case study will be handled throughout its lifecycle, from collection and processing to long-term preservation and reuse. The project integrates whole-genome sequencing data from Iberian hares with pathogen detection to investigate host-pathogen interactions underlying differential susceptibility to myxomatosis.

The purpose of this DMP is to ensure that all data are managed in accordance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), comply with legal and ethical requirements (including Nagoya Protocol considerations), and are made available to the scientific community and relevant stakeholders where appropriate. The DMP also defines procedures for data storage, backup, metadata standards, controlled access to sensitive information, and long-term archiving in trusted repositories.

Template: [FCT - Template in English](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 DATA INFORMATION

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

No

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

fastq

1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

fastq

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

>1000 GB

2 DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

https://copo-project.org/copo/copo_accessions/dashboard Manifest ID "9920bfa5-1abc-4b2a-8162-76ab372819b0"

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

Yes

2.2.2 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data.

https://copo-project.org/copo/copo_accessions/dashboard Manifest ID "9920bfa5-1abc-4b2a-8162-76ab372819b0"

2.2.4 Please identify the controlled vocabularies that apply.

COPO and ENA controlled vocabularies

3 STORAGE AND SECURITY OF DATA AND METADATA

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

No

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Default security measures of the institution networked research storage

3.2.2 Please specify.

Data is deposited in ENA and COPO

4 PERSONAL DATA, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS AND OWNERSHIP

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

No

4.1.3 How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

João Pedro Marques (0000-0001-9834-1361)

Associação BIOPOLIS - Rede de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Biologia Evolutiva

Case study leader

5 DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

5.1 Long-term data preservation

5.1.1 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?

All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least 10 years

5.2 Data available for re-use

5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

All data resulting from the project will be made available

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available as soon as archived in repository

29 december 2025

5.2.4 In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use, and under which license?

European Nucleotide Archive

5.2.5 Please confirm if:

The repository is certified

5.2.6 Please indicate whether a persistent identifier will be pursued.

Yes

DOI

5.2.7 Under which license will the data be archived and made available for re-use?

Academic Free License 3.0

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

5.2.8 Describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project.

Code will be made publicly available on GitHub

6 RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

6.1 Responsibilities and resources for data management

6.1.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?

João Pedro Marques (0000-0001-9834-1361)

Associação BIOPOLIS - Rede de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Biologia Evolutiva

Case study leader

6.1.2 What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?

A full week of the project will be dedicated to ensuring that data management follows the FAIR principles.

Powered by

